

INHERENT CURE OF CARBON FIBRE COMPOSITES USING THEIR ELECTRICAL RESISTANCE

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1 Introduction

This paper presents a study in to the cure of carbon fibre composite via electrical heating of the carbon fibres themselves. This is achieved by direct connection of the fibres to an electric current. In this way the fibres act as heating elements meaning that the resin in the immediate vicinity of each fibre will be heated, and thus cure effected. As the distance that the heat must travel in order to cause cure is very low, the heating of the resin is very rapid. Previous work on this has been limited [1], with it having been shown to be possible to cure resin in this manner, however the properties were disappointing, and the results suggested that the resin was under-cured. The current paper therefore aims to overcome these limitations and to compare fully electrically cured composite with conventional methods in order to determine the effectiveness of the process.

Manufacturing of high performance composites has relied heavily on the use of autoclaves in the past, to obtain the right combination of heat, vacuum (to remove volatiles) and pressure consolidation (to ensure maximum density of the part). This approach is costly [2], as heat transfer to the part is by convection and heating takes place from the outside of the panel. This can lead to significant temperature profiles through the thickness of the composite meaning regular dwells and slow heating rates are necessary to uniformly cure the panel [3,4]. Rates of between 1°C/min. and 4°C/min are typical. The requirement for a large pressure vessel also adds to the cost of this approach. To attempt to overcome these issues, a number of other manufacturing techniques, generically known as “out of autoclave” (OOA) techniques, have been developed.

One advantage of these OOA techniques is the heating rate that can be applied, as the thermal mass of the system is much lower. Researchers have

investigated the effect of much higher heating rates on the properties of the composite and found that if well controlled there is little if any reduction in the mechanical properties. [5]

Two processes which allow particularly rapid heating rates are Quickstep™ and microwave cure

Quickstep™ employs liquid as the heat transfer medium via a flexible mould surface. As the liquid has a low thermal mass, unlike the metal moulds used in the previous techniques, very rapid changes in temperature are possible (up to approximately 14°C/min.) [2,6]. This is in contrast to the conventional ramp rates of less than 4°C/min. Consolidation pressure is also provided by the liquid medium, so consolidation pressures similar to autoclaves are possible and, as such, no special composites are required. As with autoclave processing, heat transfer occurs from the panel surface to the centre by conduction.

Microwave cure of composites heats the part directly from within its structure, as the microwaves interact through the thickness [4,7]. As such, it therefore overcomes the problem that heat must conduct from the surface in order to warm the centre of the panel, as long as the panel is relatively thin so that the microwaves can penetrate. As heat rapidly builds up in the centre of the part, viscosity of the resin reduces throughout the panel at the same time. Therefore consolidation can take place throughout the panel at the same rate, rather than densifying the outer surfaces first and therefore trapping bubbles within the structure. The effect is a reduction of the observed void content [8].

It is therefore advantageous to heat the panel from the inside out rather than from the outside in. Unfortunately microwave cure has other disadvantages, not least the danger that the

microwaves present to humans and thus the requirement for careful containment. There is also a complication in ensuring the microwave field uniformly encompasses the part, preventing “hotspots” from forming and creating a panel with varying degrees of cure in different locations. This has been partially overcome with variable frequency microwave processing [9]. These issues add to the cost of the microwave system.

Cure of the composite by directly applying an electric current presents an alternative approach to curing that overcomes some of these difficulties. Direct application of an electrical current to a carbon-fibre causes it to heat, a fact that led to the use of carbonised threads as filaments in the early electrical light-bulbs. Utilising this effect, opens a way to cure composites in which heating occurs throughout the panel simultaneously, as with microwave cure, but without the concomitant containment problems. Indeed the system can consist merely of a power supply, electrical contacts and a vacuum bag to provide consolidation of the panel.

To date only one paper has been published using direct application of an electric current to cure composite [1], although others have used an embedded mesh to act as a heating element [10]. In the existing paper [1], the electrical current was applied by interleaving copper blocks as contacts between all of the layers of a carbon-fibre composite laminate (914c TS(6K) pre-preg sheeting produced by Hexcel Composites), at both ends of the panel. The centre of the panel was then clamped between blocks of metal to provide a consolidation pressure. Electricity was applied to the panel through the contacts, with a voltage of between 6 V and 6.4 V and a current of 15 A being necessary to successfully cure the panel. In this case, the panel was heated to 185°C and this temperature was held for 60 minutes to cure the panel. Following cure, the panel was tested using 3-point bending and it was found that the composite was tougher than conventionally cured composite (Break strain 4.1% against 2.2%), but that it had a lower maximum stress level (520 MPa against 773 MPa). These findings suggest that the composite was under-cured and that a longer cure time or a higher temperature would have been beneficial. There appears to have been no further work on this topic by the authors.

This paper therefore examines the electrical cure of composites, focussing on ensuring complete cure of the composite and determining the necessary power input to achieve it. Initially, work will focus on the contact arrangements to ensure uniform heating of the panel. Once uniform heating is obtained, work will focus on determining the length of time required to fully cure the composite. Finally, the necessary power to cure the composite will be determined and compared to that required for conventional cure.

2 Experimental

Materials and Equipment

The composite used in this study was Cycom 950-1 obtained from Cytec Engineered Materials Ltd, which has a recommended cure schedule of 2 hours at 135°C under vacuum pressure. Each sample was 14 cm by 6 cm and consisted of two plies. For electrical cure, the composite was vacuum bagged and heated electrically as described below. Additionally, panels were prepared using the recommended schedule in a curing oven, again within a vacuum bag. All vacuum consumables were obtained from Tygavac Advanced Materials Ltd.

Electrical contacts were made using DuPont Pyralux FR-8510 flexible electrical circuit board consisting of an 18µm layer of copper on a 25µm layer of polyimide film, bonded with a 25µm adhesive film.

Power was supplied using a Rapid Electronics SPS-9602 power supply rated at 30V, 30 A

Temperature of the panels was monitored using a Pico Technologies TC08 and PicoLog software, attached to three Type N thermocouples.

Thermal images were taken using an Electrophysics PV320 thermal imaging camera.

Thermal analysis of degree of cure was obtained using a Perkin Elmer DMA8000, in dual cantilever bending with samples measuring 75.0 mm x 5.0 mm x 0.7 mm. Testing was conducted at temperatures between 20°C and 250°C with a ramp rate of 3°C per minute. Three frequencies were used, those being 1 Hz, 10 Hz and 100 Hz in order to determine the location of the glass transition and to observe if residual cure was occurring.

Fig 1. Showing A. The sample with electrical connections made using a wire directly introduced between the composite plies; B. The sample with contacts made using single strips of flexible circuit board; C. The sample with contacts made using strips of flexible circuit board enclosing the edges of each ply.

Electrical Cure Process and Analysis

Several contact arrangements were considered in order to obtain a uniform temperature distribution. These are summarised in the Figure 1.

An electrical field was applied in each case and the uniformity of the heat was assessed using the thermal imaging camera and thermocouples taped to the surface of the panel. Heat in the panel was controlled manually in this initial trial. Regular adjustment of the supply was required, particularly during the initial stages of cure, as the resistance of the composite fell with the reduction in resin viscosity and increased consolidation of the component.

The cure time was varied from 8 minutes to 1 hour and the panels were sectioned to provide specimens for DMA testing. The glass transition envelopes were compared with those of the oven-cured specimen, with differences between the two indicating differences in the molecular weight distribution within the panels.

3 Results

Contact geometries

The effect of contact geometry was tested using

three different contact geometries, with the uniformity of the heating being assessed using thermocouples placed along the surface of the panel. Figure 2 shows the uniformity for sample type A, Figure 3 shows the uniformity for sample type B and Figure 4 shows the uniformity for sample type C as illustrated in Figure 1.

It is readily seen that the uniformity for sample type A is poor (Figure 2), with excess heating around the contacts, particularly the negative contact. The heat distribution with sample type B is more uniform (Figure 3), but there is still a tendency to heating only at the contacts, again with the negative contact being hotter than the positive contact. Finally, with sample type C, the temperature is much more uniform than for the previous samples (Figure 4). There is some excess heating in the contacts, but this is minimized and the temperature field is acceptably uniform for the purposes of this study. Therefore all future samples employ this contact geometry.

The reason why there should be excess heat at the negative contact compared to the positive contact is not known. However, with a number of samples tested this was always found to be the case. This suggests that the use of an alternating current might provide more uniform heating. However it was not

possible to assess this in the present study.

Fig 3. Graph showing poor uniformity of heating with electrical contacts made purely by embedding electrical wire in the panel ends.

Fig 2. Graph showing poor uniformity of heating when a single layer of flexible circuit board is used to make electrical contact with the panel.

Fig 4. Graph showing good uniformity of heating when the ends of each ply within the composite are encased between two layers of flexible circuit board.

Fig 5. Thermal image showing the uniformity of heating in the panel at (a) 5 minutes after heating started and at (b) when equilibrium had been reached.

Thermal imaging was employed to further study the heating process of the panel, particularly the uniformity as the panel initially heats. Figure 5 shows two images, a) taken 5 minutes after the start of heating and b) taken when an equilibrium temperature had been reached according to the thermocouples. From these images, it is clear that initially heating concentrates around the contacts and through the central portion of the panel. This is shown by the very edges of the panel in the vicinity of the contacts being heated, while for the rest of the panel length, the edges are notably cooler. After the panel has reached equilibrium, it is readily

apparent that heating is uniform across the panel. The edges are, however, slightly cooler as they are more efficient at radiating heat than the bulk of the panel.

Cured properties

Dynamic mechanical analysis was used to show the glass transition temperatures of the composites made using electrical cure and also made using conventional vacuum bag curing. Differences in the glass transition envelopes would show whether the panels were completely cured, or not.

The glass transition envelope of a polymer is very sensitive to under-cure, due to the presence of short-chain-length polymer. As the material approaches glass transition, short-chain-length material will undergo glass transition first, as the chains are less constrained. It will therefore be seen

testing at a lower temperature due to the principle of time/temperature superposition. Differences in the glass transition envelope at higher frequencies can therefore be related to the mobility of the structure. In essence we would expect to see the glass transition temperature increase when we test at higher frequencies. We would also hope to see

Fig 6. DMA traces for the samples cured for different times, tested at 100 Hz, showing the different glass transition envelopes.

that the glass transition envelope begins at a lower temperature. It is also possible that the peak of the glass transition envelope (the glass transition point) will be lower if the degree of cure is less, however this will depend on the proportion of the resin that remains under-cured.

whether there are any effects at the end of the glass transition envelope.

Figure 6 shows the glass transition traces for the samples tested at 100 Hz, this is typical of the tests undertaken at each frequency.

Different testing frequencies can reveal important differences in the performance of the composite. Testing at a higher frequency is equivalent to

Average glass transition temperatures at each frequency are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Average glass transition temperatures for each cure schedule at each of the tested frequencies

Frequency (Hz)	Average glass transition temperature (°C)				
	Oven	8 minutes	16 minutes	30 minutes	60 minutes
1	178	186	183	187	196
10	200	195	192	195	203
100	217	203	206	205	210

It is readily apparent that the sample electrically cured for 8 minutes displays an envelope that starts to increase from approximately 40°C and progressively rises before a peak forms at approximately 200°C. This gradual slope indicates that there is significant low molecular weight material present in the composite cured under this regime.

Considering the sample cured for 16 minutes, the envelope closely follows that of the oven-cured specimen with a fairly broad peak in the glass transition envelope suggesting a minor peak at between 140°C and 160°C and the major peak at approximately 200°C. When a cure of 30 minutes or 60 minutes is conducted, the secondary peak at approximately 150°C disappears and the main glass transition shifts slightly higher to approximately 210°C suggesting that cure is more complete than in the oven cured specimen and also in those cured for less time.

Energy consumption in electric cure

From these results it is readily apparent that it is possible to cure composites using directly applied electric current. However, the question arises as to whether it is energy efficient to do so. Taking preliminary data for the cure of composites using directly applied electric current, the following analysis can be performed to determine the power per unit volume of composite. This can then be compared to that required for oven cure to see if electric cure is worthwhile or not. The results of this analysis are shown in Table 2. In the analysis, it is assumed that the oven is curing the largest possible panel area (40 cm by 60 cm), with a thickness of 2mm, the heating rate is assumed to be 2°C per minute and the cure time to be 2 hours (total time 170 minutes). The electrically cured specimen size is taken to be that used in the actual process, as are the voltage and current values. The cure time is taken as 40 minutes, which consists of the ramp time (10 minutes) plus the 30 minutes cure time.

From this analysis it is apparent that the direct application of electrical current has the potential to save significant power over conventional cure processes. It should be noted, however, that the principle saving in power is in the saving of time by shortening the cure process. In terms of the power per unit volume, the figures are relatively similar. However, the necessarily slow temperature ramp of the oven, at 2°C per minute, and the 2 hour cure time, mean that the overall power consumption of the oven cure is approximately 3 times the power used in the electrical cure process.

Faster ramp rates are possible with electric cure as the heat is created within the composite, so the whole thickness of the composite quickly comes to temperature. In the case of oven cure, the temperature rise in the panel is controlled by convection within the oven and conduction from the surface of the composite in to the centre. As this is a slow process, slow ramp rates are required to ensure that cure occurs uniformly through the thickness. The ramp rates possible with direct electric cure of the composite are akin to those that can be obtained using the Quickstep™ process, where only conduction within the resin limits the ramp rate. With this technique ramp-rates of >10°C per minute have been shown to be possible and indeed to have little effect on the properties of the finished article. It is therefore likely that the same will be true for the electrical cure process, although this needs to be verified.

If verification of mechanical properties shows that fast ramp rates are possible, the opportunity for energy saving with electrical cure are significant, making the process financially and environmentally desirable.

Table 2. Showing the power consumption of the optimised electrical cure process and the oven cure process

	Sample volume (cm ³)	Voltage (V)	Current (A)	Total power (Wmin)	Power per unit volume (Wmin/cm ³)
Electric cure	5.88	3.5	11.5	1610	274
Oven cure	480	240	10	408000	850

4. Conclusions

Cure of composites by the direct application of electric current to the fibres is a practical production technique for laboratory-scale specimens. However, the connection procedure needs to be optimised to ensure uniform heat distribution.

Such specimens can have degree of cure similar to those obtained by conventional cure methods according to manufacturers recommended schedules.

The cure can occur in substantially less time due to removal of ramp-rate restrictions as the path-length for conduction is greatly reduced.

Using this approach, the energy consumption for cure of the composite can be significantly reduced.

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